

2022

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

ENSURING EFFICIENCY IN ORGANIZATION ACTIVITY

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Abstract: The main role in the content and essence of marketing activities is given to the consumer, which reflects the objective conditions of market development, which to a certain extent loses its independence and falls under the regulatory influence of pre-established economic relations.

Key words: Marketing, philosophy, market development, consumer.

The marketing philosophy is very simple: the manufacturer must produce such a product that it must be sold, and the level of profitability and profit set by the firm must be ensured.

The main role in the content and essence of marketing activities is given to the consumer, which reflects the objective conditions of market development, which to a certain extent loses its independence and falls under the regulatory influence of pre-established economic relations.

The consumer puts forward his requirements for the product within its technical and economic framework and thus creates an opportunity for market sharing among producers. The importance of competition and struggle for the consumer in the market is increasing, and it sets high demands on product quality and competitiveness. Such a situation forces a deep and careful study of market needs and specific potential consumers.

It accelerates the scientific and technical process of product demand under

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consumer pressure, fully takes into account consumer demand in the production program and implements a program-targeted approach to production, increases competitiveness and makes management decisions, applies the principles of centralization and decentralization. shib stipulates the need to use the most convenient management system. Therefore, the task of ensuring mutual effectiveness of various levels of management functions such as planning, control, organization and leadership in marketing is very important.

In the implementation of marketing activities, the demands and needs of consumers, market demand participate as an objective necessity in taking into account the scientific and technical, production, and sales activities of the firm.

The marketing activity of the firm is sufficient, based on the needs of the market, the concrete current and, most importantly, the long-term (strategic) goal, the ways to achieve it, and the real sources of economic activity resources: product quality and assortment, its important directions, production aimed at defining a convenient system and the desired profit. Two factors play the main role in modern marketing: firstly, scientific and technical development, along with it, the strongest condition for production development and the increasing importance of the human factor in the form of quality, which does not affect the growth rate and the income of employees.

Secondly, at the same time, social needs will grow. In such conditions, when the competition and struggle are growing with particular intensity, the world market suddenly becomes stronger as a result of dividing the spheres of influence among large corporations.

This situation has a significant impact on the adaptation of first large, then

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medium, and gradually small companies to market demand on the one hand, and on the formation of such demand on the other hand. This process intensified under the influence of the scientific and technical revolution. Thus, consumer pressure, which has become the norm, was created. In other words, it became necessary for the manufacturer to produce a product that is quickly sold and brings great profit. For this, it is necessary to study social and individual needs, to study the market demand that creates the basis for production as a necessary condition. Therefore, the understanding that production begins with consumption, not exchange, is deepening.

This concept found its expression in marketing. Thus, the main task of marketing activities is to correctly target production based on market demand by understanding needs and demands.

Marketing is a management system with its own principles, function, system, regulatory and legal acts:

1. The main principle of marketing is the fundamental freedom of survival strategy and targeting.
2. A comprehensive approach to the relationship between the company's capabilities and resources.
3. Convenient connection of centralized and decentralized management.

Marketing functions designed to implement this principle:

complete and accurate calculation of consumer demand, supply and market demand;

determination of a convenient range of products;

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making effective decisions based on the last results of the enterprise's activity; development of a sales policy based on the formation of consumer needs and sales promotion system, organization of after-sales technical service, product movement system, determination of the most profitable sales channels. To implement this function, it provides feedback with the market in order to adjust the calculation within the framework of the marketing program for decision-making at the appropriate level of management.

Marketing is the core of program marketing. Each department of the company is based on the production of one type of product.

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